

INFLUENCE OF **ADDITIVES** AND **FIBER-LAYUP** ON THE AGING BEHAVIOR OF **HIGH-TEMPERATURE** EPOXY RESIN PREPREG SYSTEMS

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Air Travel is back! – But Strong Impact on Climate Change

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Trend towards lower CO₂ emissions for rail and car traffic
 Aviation expected to grow to **Pre-Covid level** latest **2024**

Aviation is fastest-growing Source of Greenhouse Emissions

Air traffic threatens to become the **largest CO₂ polluter** by 2050

Solutions:

- Flying less
- New propulsion systems
- Biobased fuels
- Lightweight design and material

Emissions at high altitude have **2-4x times** greater impact than comparable ground emissions

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Development of FRP in Aviation

Development of FRP in Aviation – Quo Vadis?

Further increase through replacement of aluminium, titanium alloys by

high-temperature resistant polymer composites

for

- Engine fairings
- Air ducts
- Guide vanes
- etc.

High-Temperature Resin Systems

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Motivation for the Research

High- T_g Epoxy Resin System – Technical Aims

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State of the Art

4,4'-Diaminodiphenyl sulfone

Overview of Chosen Material System

HP-7250

Functionality: 5.0
by DIC Corporation (Japan)

High T_g
Epoxy
resin system

Exolit OP935

Particle size D50: $2\mu\text{m}$
Content: 10 wt.%
by Clariant AG (Germany)

FR

Toughener

4,4'-Diaminodiphenyl sulfone

by ACCI Specialty Materials (USA)

Sumikaexcel 5003P

Hydroxy-terminated PES powder
Particle size $20\mu\text{m}$
Content: 20 wt.%
By Sumitomo Chemicals (Japan)

Experimental Design

N₂

Factors:

Time

Temperature

Additives

Atmosphere

Outputs:

Dimensional

Thermal

Mechanical

Fire related

Methods – Design of Experiments (DoE)

Full factorial design
 two factors at 225 °C + air → 2D:

● : Experiments

Partial factorial design (Taguchi)
 four factors → 4D:

Properties

Outputs:

Dimensional

Thermal

Mechanical

Fire related

Outputs

Full Factorial DoE– Thermal Properties: DMA

- Converging trends ~ 270 °C
- Significant factor: **time**
- No impact on T_g of the PES phase

Outputs

Full Factorial DoE– Mechanical Properties: 3-PBb

- Converging trends to ~4000 MPa
- Significant factor: **time**

- Strong drop after 125 h
- Significant factor: **time**

- Strong drop at 125 h
- Significant factor: **time**

Full Factorial DoE– Mechanical Properties: CT

- 1) Crack-bridging
- 2) Crack-pinning
- 3) Crack path deflection
- 4) Particle-induced shear banding

Outputs

Full Factorial DoE – Fire Properties: CCT

- Strong drop by adding FR and FR/T
- Significant factor: **additive** and **time**

- Enhanced smoking at 0 h
- **No** significant factors, large model error

- Lower intumescence

Prepreg Processing

Style 7781 Glass-Fabric
satin 8H weave pattern
Weight 295 g/m²

Laminate Manufacturing

Crossply Laminate

$(0/90)_{4s}$

Lay-up on heating table (50% FVC)

- for shear-loaded parts
- for pipes/ducts

Curing Process

Curing Cycle:

1h 120 °C/3h 180

Free-Standing Tempering 1h at 250 °C

Laminate Manufacturing

Crossply Laminate

$(0/90)_{4s}$

- for shear-loaded parts
- for pipes/ducts

Quasi-Isotropic Laminate

$[45/90/-45/0]_{2s}$

Lay-up on heating table (50% FVC)

- Standard lay-up

Curing Process

Curing Cycle:
1h 120 °C/3h 180

Free-Standing Tempering 1h at 250 °C

Influence of Aging on Interlaminar Shear Stress

Stronger drop in crossply laminate due to **higher thermal stress** in **0/90 direction**

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Influence of Aging on Interlaminar Shear Stress

Quasi-Isotropic Layup

Minor cracks visible in nitrogen atmosphere

Influence of Aging on Interlaminar Shear Stress

Quasi-Isotropic Layup

Wider cracks with higher occurrence visible in air atmosphere

Influence of Fiber Reinforcement on Aging Behaviour

N₂ Atmosphere

Air Atmosphere

Influence of Fiber Reinforcement on Aging Behaviour

Composite shows **higher weight loss** due to **sizing degradation** and pathways
 Linear degradation in N₂, oxidation leads to higher weight loss in air

Summary of Results

- I. High- T_g epoxy resin system developed with **temperature-stable additives** suitable for **prepreg processing**
- II. **Influence of toughener and flame-retardant** on thermal degradation, mechanical properties and flame retardant properties
- III. Influence of **fiber-reinforcement** on aging behavior determined

Next Steps...

Determination of the **influence of additives** on the isothermal aging behavior on **GFRP** and **CFRP** composite

Determination of **the influence of additives** on the temperature cyclic aging behavior on **GFRP** and **CFRP** composite

Life time prediction for neat, additivated resin system and laminate with *Netzsch Kinetics Neo*

Questions?

Aging...
You can't avoid it.....

